

Indonesian Value Education Strategy Through History Learning with Local Hero Theme

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ABSTRACT: Textually speaking, this study aims to enhance Indonesian values through teaching history on the theme of local heroes. Heroes are usually associated with local principles, traditions, and cultures. Building and preserving local identity and pride was greatly helped by local heroes. Their contribution is in accordance with the needs and characteristics of the community. This research was conducted qualitatively and using literary studies. The results of the research suggest that, firstly, the understanding of local heroes must be relevant to classroom history teaching from a philosophical and pedagogical point of view; secondly, fears or apriori about the emergence of primordialism or ethnocentrism in local history education must be eliminated; and thirdly, educators and historians, not students, must create popular ideas like a local hero.

KEYWORDS: Indonesian Value Strategy, History Study, Local Heroes

I. INTRODUCTION

With 16,771 islands from Sabang to Merauke, Indonesia has a wide variety of tribes, beliefs, languages, religions, cultures, and customs. Across the world, it is estimated that there are 184 independent countries, consisting of 5,000 ethnic groups and 600 language groups. Recent data show that one-fifth of all ethnicities in the world are in Indonesia, which has more than 1,000 ethnic or subethnic groups [1]. Many of these ethnic groups are often a concern, which can cause many problems and can break up due to linguistic, political, and economic differences [2]. In order to strengthen the sense of student nationalism and instill the values of heroism in local communities, historical learning strategies must be used to unite about how the country stands and remains tolerant and humble as a multicultural nation.

One factor that causes the memory of local people to fade is that local people's phrases are no longer discussed in public spaces or in schools. As a result, people become unaware of the local people, even though they have made a significant contribution to the local community's survival. It is also influenced by social changes that build social structures, social values, and social trends gradually. Less character-shaping family environments, less emphasis on the values of heroism in the school curriculum and social changes can gradually change the way students see and prioritize the Values of Heroism.

Each generation has a different experience, so the memories passed from one generation to the next can be different, even though they remain related to the same events, characters, and artifacts. Halbwachs (2011:54) states that "the process, given that it is a collective process, part of a social process, is always open to processes of interpretation and change". For that, learning history is essential to instilling nationalism, patriotism, and character. The pursuit of history is one of the subjects to be studied by students. By studying it, students will gain a deep understanding of past events and can take the example of influential people in the past [3]. "Local Hero" is a term used to refer to a person in a particular community or area who is considered a hero or leader [4]. This term is usually used to describe someone who has a positive impact on the community around him through real actions and contributions [5]. A local hero can be an example to others around him, either through kindness, courage, leadership, or a real contribution to improving the quality of life of those around him. Because of their dedication and contributions that have an impact on the everyday lives of the people around them, they are often known and respected by the local community [6], [7].

Some of the things to bear in mind when using the concept of local hero in education and historical research are as follows: 1) local heroes are real characters who perform heroic acts in the social, economic, and political spheres, etc; 2) Explanations and research about local supporters must be associated with a great momentum in a series of historical events so that their historical value is not disturbed; 3) local Heroes are usually known through oral storytelling, so oral history methods should be used; 4) Reading or understanding a local hero requires critical understanding so that readers and researchers are not trapped in primitive or even ethnocentric narratives; 5) Regressive paradigms will make local hero more interesting to study; and 6) Foucault concepts are found behind their macro narratives [8]–[10]. Local Hero, a creative idea, can't be released from the memory of the community.

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Therefore, more in-depth examination relates to the values that can be acquired through historical learning and the social construction of a society that will provide information about the kiprah.

Characters who have great influence at the local level Their names are buried in official history stories that are taught strictly in schools and universities. Although most of the characters are old. This local hero is a historical overview of a region with its location or, more often, geographical elements. Local history refers to the history of places that have local values and treaties. It has many cores and has a broad meaning. In addition to the things mentioned above, looking at local history also means looking at how a particular person or group experienced things in the past. The events are based on much of the original historical evidence and are placed in a regional and national comparative context.

II. METHODOLOGY

The researchers looked at the data they obtained using a qualitative approach. According to Cresswell [11] , the descriptive quantitative approach gathers information about social problems using documents Sugiyono [12] Sugiyono then stated that although literary and descriptional qualitatively studies may be simple methods, they can analyze the data thoroughly according to the available sources.

This research uses a method of literature study. Collecting data based on scientific articles, books, and related written sources is part of this method [13]. The aim of this literature review is to strengthen and strengthen conception by using library sources to obtain data and based on relevant and previously conducted empirical research [14]. In this study, the researcher compared the various books, articles, and scripts he wrote about the history of local heroes and their important role in student Indonesian value-building strategies.

In the study of literature, researchers can do the following: (1) collect initial data, such as books, scientific articles, journals, and other written sources relevant to the subject of research; (2) process data by briefly deducting the correlations between the categories analysed; and (3) draw initial conclusions, which are flexible, which means that they can be changed if new benefits are found. [15]

IV. RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

History learning is an educational process aimed at acquiring an understanding of past events, important figures, cultures, and changes taking place in society. Learning about local heroes has many benefits as students not only gain a better understanding of the history of their region, but also learn to appreciate the cultural and historical heritage of their neighborhood. The particular impact of this is the formation of the social identity of students in addition to opening their eyes. Expected students will find their own identity. As a result, local heroic stories will encourage students to think critically about social events. Some of the following things can be learned from historical learning with the theme of local heroes when evaluated:

1. **Materials Selection** In education, choosing materials about local heroes can be an effective way to inculcate principles of heroism and appreciate the contribution of the local hero to society. Correctly chosen materials can help students shape their identities and enhance their understanding of the importance of principles in local contexts.
2. **Local Relevance** In order to build a strong relationship between students and the principles of heroism taught, local relevance in the selection of hero material is crucial. Involving the elements of local relevancy in the choice of heroic material helps students gain a more meaningful learning experience, deepen their understanding of the heroism principles, and encourage them to participate actively in history and character learning.
3. **Narrative Stories** Interesting narrative stories about local heroes can play an important role in motivating and inspiring students. Teachers can create interesting learning experiences, motivate students, and encourage them to think critically about the values of heroism that exist in the environment where they live.
4. **Curriculum Integration** Integrating local heroes into the curriculum can ensure that the material is not only complementary, but also an essential part of learning. In this way, teachers can give students a deep and meaningful learning experience, as well as enrich their understanding of the history and values of heroism in their local environment.

This is an example of the analysis of the literature review of local heroes.

No	Penulis	Judul	Nilai Pahlawan	Nilai Keindonesiaan	Referensi
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ganda Febri Kurniawan• Wardo Wardo• Leo Agung Sutimin	Local Heroes Into History Class: Criticism of Ideological Hegemony in Heroic History Narrating	To find out to what extent students can gain critical understanding through the concept, researchers tried to link the idea of local heroes with critical pedagogy.	educational and philosophical aspects, concerns or doubts about the emergence of ethnocentrism or primordialism in the study of local history	[16]
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Nurul Monica Lestari	A.K. Gani National Hero Museum as a Local	Historical resources such as museums, sites, or similar historical learning	Cultural reserves can be used as sources of local history to reveal various types of local	[17]

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> L.R. Retno Susanti 	History Resource in History Learning	resources are other ways that can help acquire additional knowledge and acquire the social skills necessary to interact with the Society.	uniqueness and intelligence that originate from older local cultures. National history lessons often ignore this information.	
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sumargono Vany Aswandi Imroah Laina Retno Mukti Kusuma 	Lary: Historical learning media innovation based on local heroes of Lampung as an attempt to integrate character education for the Golden Generation	Adherence to positive values when instilling these values in students can teach them about the importance of the values of unity and unity, as well as hard work and reluctance to surrender.	Heroes often show the value of dedication and dedication to society and nation.	[18]
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ismail Haliadi Windayanti Wilman Darsono Lumangino 	Socialization of Historical Books of Local Heroes (Towalangi Di Kulawi) District of Sigi for Learning Materials of Indonesian History in Sma State 12 Sigi	The phenomena related to family history, social history, hero role, culture, ethnic origin, and various local events can be caused by the elasticity of local history.	Heroes who fight for justice and humanity, whether in the social or political sphere, reflect the values of human rights and justice, which are the foundations of the state.	[19]

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1. Teacher and Teacher Training: Training teachers and educators to understand, internalize, and impart Indonesian values to students in the right way.
2. Out-of-class activities and leadership: Participate in out-of - class activities that support Indonesian values, such as gotong royong, art, and culture, as well as leadership based on Indonesians values.
3. Collaboration with local communities: Involve the local community in the educational process to disseminate local values that are consistent with local culture and traditions.
4. Use of Educational Technology: Creatively and intriguingly, use educational technology, such as interactive learning applications and online learning, to teach Indonesian values.
5. Development of Learning Materials: Create interesting and relevant learning materials that describe Indonesian values in various contexts of everyday life.

By applying Indonesian values education strategies, it is expected that younger generations will understand, appreciate, and apply the values of Indonesia in their daily lives, so that they can strengthen their national identity and build a cultural society.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the stories above, there are three things to bear in mind: first, the idea of a local hero must be relevant to teaching in a history class from a philosophical and pedagogical point of view; second, the fear or apriori about the emergence of a sense of primordialism or ethnosentrism in studying local history must be eliminated; and third, popular ideas such as a local Hero must be created by educators and historians, not students. Formal education, social interaction, and character education are some of the ways that can be used to enhance Indonesian values and shape student patriotism.

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